

REMOTE LEARNING CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF GRADE 9 LEARNERS IN TAMBLER DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the remote learning challenges and coping mechanisms of Grade 9 learners in Tambler District. Quantitative data were administered from the three secondary schools namely: Banisil National High School, Bawing National High School, and Colot S. Aligado IP High School. A total of 267 learners participated. The challenges were categorized into the following: Self-Regulation Challenges, Technological Literacy and Competency Challenges, Student Isolation Challenges, Learning Resource challenges and Learning Environment Challenges. These challenges were analyzed in the context of specific coping mechanisms, namely: Adaptation, Cognitive Aptitude Enhancement, Goal-setting, Peer learning, and Relaxation and Recreation Strategies. Based on the findings, it was found that Technological Competency challenges has the lowest salient met by learners. Different coping mechanisms were employed to cope with these challenges. The least commonly used method was the peer-learning which ranked fifth among other strategies. Hence, among the schools, the learners in Colot Aligado IP School have experienced the greatest extent of challenges and the lowest extent of challenges is experienced by the learners of Banisil National High School.

Keywords: *Remote Learning, Grade 9 Learners, Coping Mechanisms*

INTRODUCTION

Remote learning has been adopted as an alternative means of education even before the COVID-19 pandemic struck the whole world. Its first use was traced as early

as 1858, when the University of London became the first university to offer distance learning courses (eLearning Industry). The objectives of distance learning are straightforward. It was designed as an alternative means of learning for students, learners, and institutions that are facing difficulties when it comes to physical or face-to-face classroom setups.

However, the implementation of remote learning isn't that simple, especially on countries where the physical and support infrastructures needed for this setup aren't that readily established. For instance, Philippines ranks low when it comes to internet speed and connectivity as compared to other ASEAN countries (Philstar, 2020). Furthermore, majority of its population are in the marginalized sectors, proving that their access to laptops, computers, and conducive learning environments outside school is limited.

In National Context, during the advent of COVID-19, the Philippine school system was forced to adopt the remote learning setup to ensure the continuity of learning and prevent the educational sector from collapsing. Despite the efforts of the Department of Education, Commission on Higher Education, and other linked agencies, remote learning has been a difficult world to navigate, especially in public schools situated in rural areas. The global pandemic has exposed our current education systems' flaws and disparities. Building resilience begins with school cultures and individual attitudes toward implementing new teaching and learning strategies (Microsoft et. al, 2020).

Remote learning, despite being applied to practice by various academic institutions, is still a discipline that requires further analysis and exploration. Specifically, there's no in-depth, comprehension research that compares the effectiveness of remote learning and traditional learning. As a research gap, it is an important analysis as it will showcase the viability of remote learning as a standard means of teaching. As recently observed, June Ahn and Andre McEachin (2017) have exhibited the adverse sides of remote learning to students across secondary and primary schools. It found that students in these schools have lower Math and reading grades than those enrolled in traditional schools. It also has been shown that parents have struggled in the remote learning setup. They have expressed that their children have difficulties keeping up with their school tasks. Aside from that, they are worried that their children aren't as motivated as when they are schooling in physical classrooms.

In the Local context, Tumbler District, three of its secondary schools are in agro-industrial areas—which are mostly rural in nature. Because of this, many students don't have access to stable internet connections, laptops, computers, and even smartphones. Furthermore, they experienced difficulties in coping with the modules, given that they are more used to the traditional learning approach rather than the self-taught one.

To respond to this problem, schools must create strategies to further lessen the problems experienced by learners in the remote learning setup, analyze all the limitations of remote learning, and reveal the different strategies learners used, and how it can be improved for future implementation. It is along with these reasons that the researcher was prompted to pioneer this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the outcomes of remote learning challenges and coping mechanisms of Grade 9 learners of Tumbler District. Specifically, the following research questions were addressed:

1. What is the extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners
 - 1.1 Self regulation challenges;
 - 1.2 Technological literacy and competency;
 - 1.3 Student Isolation;
 - 1.4 Learning resource; and
 - 1.5 Learning environment?
2. What is the most common coping mechanisms employed by selected Grade 9 learners of Tumbler District
 - 2.1 Adaptation
 - 2.2 Cognitive aptitude enhancement;
 - 2.3 Goal- setting
 - 2.4 Peer-learning; and
 - 2.5 Relaxation and recreation?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of challenges experienced by the Grade 9 learners in Tumbler District?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced program may be designed to alleviate the challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners across schools in Tumbler District?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the descriptive-comparative methods research design. The primary idea of this strategy suggests that quantitative data and results provide a general picture of the research problem; more analysis. When it comes to quantitative element, descriptive-comparative.

The respondents of the study consisted of 267 Grade 9 students of Deped-Gensan Tumbler District who were identified through purposive sampling. They were chosen regardless of their age and gender. The respondents were appropriated based on the school size. This technique is appropriate for this study as Cresswell, and Plano Clark (2011) implied that purposive sampling is identifying and selecting individuals or group of people who are particularly informed or experienced about a subject of interest. It covered three public high schools: Banisil National High School Bawing National High School and Colot Aligado IP High School. These participants have been engaged in remote learning for at least two years in both synchronous and asynchronous modalities.

In conducting the study, firstly, the researcher constructed a letter of permission to the Schools Division Superintendent of Department of Education in General Santos City.

Likewise, a letter of permission was also given to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Tumbler District as well as to the Principals and School Head of three public high schools in the District allowing her in the conduct the study. She then asked permission to the *National Commission on Indigenous People* Regional Office to conduct the said study.

Upon the approval of the letter, she then talked to the curriculum head of Grade 9 for the administration of the said study. With that, informed consent was sought from the participants prior to their involvement. Before students signed the informed consent form, they were oriented about the objectives of the study and the extent of their involvement. They were also briefed about the confidentiality of information, their anonymity, and their right to refuse to participate in the investigation.

Finally, the respondents were informed that there was no additional cost from their participation. The questionnaire was conducted online via Google form, Facebook Messenger and/or Google meet, respectively for the learners who have access in the internet such as in the case of Banisil National High School and Bawing National High School. For the case of learners in Colot Aligado IP High School where technology is hardly reached and gadgets such as cellular phones were not widely available, a hard copy of the questionnaires were given to them provided that health protocol and social distancing were followed. And since most of them speak Blaan dialect, an interpreter-teacher who is a pure blooded Blaan together with the researcher visited the school premise to guide them in answering.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme is described using five indicators. These are self- regulation challenges technological literacy and competency, student isolation, learning resource, and learning environment.

Table 1 The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Self-regulation Challenges (SRC)

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
I...			
1. delay tasks related to my studies so that they are either not fully completed by their deadline or had to be rushed to be completed.	3.22	1.106	Moderate Extent

2. fail to get appropriate help during online or modular classes.	3.10	1.047	Moderate Extent
3. lack the ability to control my own thoughts, emotions, and actions during online or modular classes.	3.15	1.109	Moderate Extent
4. have limited preparation before an online or modular class.	3.20	1.138	Moderate Extent
5. have poor time management skills during online or modular classes.	3.02	1.095	Moderate Extent
6. fail to properly use online or modular peer learning strategies (i.e., learning from one another to better facilitate learning such as peer tutoring, group discussion, and peer feedback).	3.02	1.088	Moderate Extent
Mean	3.12	.64666	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

Table 1 show the extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Self-Regulation Challenges (SRC). The top two challenges encountered by the learners are they delay tasks related to their studies so that they are either not fully completed by their deadline or had to be rushed to be completed ($M = 3.22$) and they have limited preparation before an online or modular class ($M = 3.20$). Both are described as moderate extent.

This means that the learners sometimes fail to perform their assignments and activities on time hence they cram as the deadlines are about to come. In addition, they have poor time management skills during online or modular classes ($M = 3.02$) and they fail to properly use online or modular peer learning strategies for example learning from one another to better facilitate learning such as peer tutoring, group discussions, and peer feedbacks ($M = 3.02$).

This has a mean of 3.12 which is also described as moderate extent. This result indicates that the learners meet challenges when they do not do their tasks immediately. When they daily-daily their work, they would really be encountering challenges. The results reflect to what Zimmerman (2012) mentioned about self-regulation, stating that it is an important aspect for young learners to be able manage their actions and reactions

in various learning process. Meanwhile, those who have poor self-regulation skills would be overwhelmed by the challenges they encounter.

Table 2. The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Technological literacy and competency challenges (TLCC)

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
I...			
7. lack competence and proficiency in using various interfaces or systems that allow me to control a computer or another embedded system for studying.	3.16	1.038	Moderate Extent
8.resist learning technology.	3.10	1.094	Moderate Extent
9.am distracted by an overly complex technology.	3.06	1.117	Moderate Extent
10. have difficulties in learning a new technology.	2.96	1.051	Moderate Extent
11. lack the ability to effectively use technology to facilitate learning.	3.10	1.062	Moderate Extent
12. lack knowledge and training in the use of technology.	3.09	1.079	Moderate Extent
13.am intimidated by the technologies used for learning.	3.08	1.061	Moderate Extent
14. resist and/or am confused when getting appropriate help during online or modular classes.	2.95	1.123	Moderate Extent

15.have poor understanding of directions and expectations during online or modular learning.	3.07	1.123	Moderate Extent
16.perceive technology as a barrier to getting help from others during online or modular classes.	2.99	1.007	Moderate Extent
Mean	3.06	.61930	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

Relative to **Technological Literacy and Competency Challenges (TLCC)** in Table 2 the learners have encountered challenges that they lack competence and proficiency in using various interfaces or systems that allow them to control a computer or another embedded system for studying ($M = 3.16$), they resist learning technology ($M = 3.10$), and they lack the ability to effectively use technology to facilitate learning ($M = 3.10$). Moreover, they meet challenges in learning a new technology ($M = 2.96$) and in resisting or they are confused when getting appropriate help during online or modular classes ($M = 2.95$). These are all described as moderate extent. This includes the mean of 3.06 which is also described as moderate extent. This shows that the learners have average difficulties in technological literacy. They have average knowledge on how to use various interfaces in the computers or systems that allow them to control a computer or another embedded system for studying.

They moderately have difficulties in learning the technology and they know how to facilitate their knowledge using the technology. This was reflected based from European Commission (2017) stating that in today's quickly digitizing world and information economy, digital literacy is now necessary for successfully living, studying, and working. This is the new reality of modern life, as illustrated by governments' growing worry that many citizens lack basic digital skills.

Table 3. The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Student isolation Challenges (SIC)

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
I...			
17. feel emotionally disconnected or isolated during online or modular classes.	3.11	1.132	Moderate Extent

18. feel disinterested during online or modular class.	2.91	1.132	Moderate Extent
19. feel unease and uncomfortable in using video projection, microphones, and speakers.	3.09	1.112	Moderate Extent
20. feel uncomfortable being the center of attention during online or modular classes.	3.25	1.155	Moderate Extent
Mean	3.09	.78341	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

In the case of **Student Isolation Challenges (SIC)**, the top is the students feel uncomfortable being the center of attention during the online or modular classes ($M = 3.25$) and the lowest is they feel disinterested during the online or modular classes ($M = 2.91$). Taken as a whole, it obtains a mean of 3.09 and is described as moderate extent. This shows that the students sometimes feel alone in their online classes. They feel disconnected and uneasy when they are called or tease during online classes.

They also sometimes feel not interested in the topics at hand. Curtis (2020) stated that when students are solitary, they may contact instructors at all hours, make many attempts to engage in nonacademic issues, and speak negatively about themselves.

Table 4. The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Learning Resource Challenges (LRC)

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
I...			
21. have an insufficient access to library resources.	3.12	1.047	Moderate Extent
22. have an insufficient access to laboratory			Moderate Extent

equipment and materials.	3.22	1.124	
23. have limited access to textbooks, worksheets, and other instructional materials.	3.19	1.140	Moderate Extent
24. experience financial challenges when accessing learning resources and technology.	3.18	1.126	Moderate Extent
Mean	3.18	.77417	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

On the **Learning Resource Challenge (LRC)**, the highest among the indicators is the insufficient access to laboratory equipment and materials ($M = 3.22$) and the lowest is the learners have an insufficient access to library resources ($M = 3.12$). The mean of 3.18 is described as moderate extent. This shows that the learners have moderate extent of challenges in the learning resource. It was also posited by Padmanabhan (2013) stating textbooks and resource materials are vital elements for effective teaching and learning. Furthermore, adequate human resource planning for appropriate instructional materials and physical infrastructure to support educational initiatives is vital.

Table 5. The extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Learning environment Challenges (LEC)

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
I...			
25. experience online distractions such as social media during online or modular classes.	3.33	1.158	Moderate Extent

26. experience distractions at home as a learning environment.	3.26	1.123	Moderate Extent
27. have difficulties in selecting the best time and area for learning at home.	3.17	1.090	Moderate Extent
28. home set-up limits the completion of certain requirements for my subject (e.g., laboratory and physical activities).	3.21	1.120	Moderate Extent
Mean	3.24	.80931	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

Table 5 presents the extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme in terms of Learning Environment Challenges (LEC). On top of the responses is they experience online distractions such as social media during online or modular classes ($M = 3.33$) and the lowest is they have difficulties in selecting the best time and area for learning at home ($M = 3.17$). Both are described as moderate extent. This has an over-all mean of 3.24 which is also described as moderate extent. This means that the learners have also experienced average extent of challenges in terms of the learning environment. Although they have experience online problems such as limited home learning environment connectivity and social media distraction, these are just to average extent. The results reflect to what UNESCO (2020) mentioned that learning environment challenges issues can have an impact on a range of educational components, including the crucial student-teacher contact for student progress. However, this demonstrated that learning can continue through distant education, particularly through digital methods, without students' physical presence in classrooms, despite some limitations.

Table 6. Summary on the extent of challenges encountered by the Grade 9 learners in the remote learning scheme

Indicator	WM	Std. Deviation	Description
Self-Regulation Challenges (SRC)	3.12	.64666	Moderate Extent

Technological Literacy and Competency Challenges (TLCC)	3.06	.61930	Moderate Extent
Student Isolation Challenges (SIC)	3.09	.78341	Moderate Extent
Learning Resource Challenges (LRC)	3.18	.77417	Moderate Extent
Learning Environment Challenges (LEC)	3.24	.80931	Moderate Extent
Over-all Mean	3.14	.54898	Moderate Extent

Legend: Very high extent- 4.50-5.00; Highly extent- 3.50-4.49; Moderately extent- 2.50-3.49; Low extent- 1.50-2.49; Very low extent-1.00-1.49

In the summary, **the learning environment** is the **highest challenge** met by the learners with **mean of 3.24**. This is followed by **learning resource challenge** with **mean of 3.18**. The least challenge they met is in the **technological literacy and competency challenge with the mean of 3.06**. **An over-all mean of 3.14 is described as moderate extent**. This implies that the learners have encountered many distractions through social media and even at home distractions. However, these distractions are manageable. This is in line with what Hobbs (2020) said that a significant number of students have difficulties in coping up with the setup due to the absence of technologies and support infrastructure. Teachers who have no experience in remote learning also encountered difficulties in disseminating lessons and assignments. The ranking of coping strategies used by the Grade 9 learners in Tambler District are presented in table 3. The indicators include adaptation, cognitive aptitude enhancement, goal- setting, peer-learning, and relaxation and recreation.

Table 7. The ranking of coping strategies used by the Grade 9 learners in Tambler District

Coping Strategies	SRC		TLCC		SIC		LRC		LEC	
	f	rank	f	rank	f	rank	f	rank	f	rank
Adaptation	134	(2)	126	(3)	103	(5)	114	(1)	71	(1)
Cognitive Aptitude Enhancement	105	(4)	146	(1)	118	(1)	95	(2)	53	(5)

Goal-setting	120	(3)	112	(4)	107	(3)	79	(4)	58	(2)
Peer-learning	76	(5)	128	(2)	112	(2)	89	(3)	56	(3)
Relaxation and recreation	141	(1)	105	(5)	104	(4)	75	(5)	56	(4)

Legend: SRC=Self-regulation challenges; TLC= Technological literacy and competency challenges; SIC= Student isolation challenges; LRC= Learning resource challenges; LEC= Learning environment challenges

Table 7 presents the ranking of coping strategies used by the Grade 9 learners in Tumbler District. Relative to **Self-regulation challenges**, the learners usually applied in relaxation and recreation (f=141), followed by adaptation (f=134), goal-setting (f=120), then Cognitive aptitude enhancement (f=105) and Peer-learning is least used in self-regulation challenges with f=76.

This supports the statement of Center for intercultural human service (2012) that relaxation can be quite beneficial in combating and managing stress and anxiety. It is necessary to always have good relaxation strategies to avoid stress.

On **Technological literacy and competency challenges**, the learners ranked cognitive aptitude enhancement as first (f=146), followed by peer-learning (f=128), then adaptation (f=126), and goal-setting (f=112) and the least used is relaxation and recreation with f=105. This was reflected based on Farah et. Al (2014) stating that the greatest significant advancements in the ability to process information have been made in computers and information technology to date. And the list of potential internal, biological upgrades has gradually grown as cognitive neuroscience has progressed.

On **student isolation challenges**, the rank 1 is using cognitive aptitude enhancement with (f=118), followed by peer-learning with f=112 in their coping strategies, then goal setting (f=107), and relaxation and recreation (f=104). The lowest is adaptation with f=103 In line with Farah et. Al (2014) statement that the amplification or expansion of core capacities of the mind by improvement or augmentation of internal or external information processing systems can be improved through different targeted interventions.

In **learning resource challenges**, the highest coping strategy of the learners is adaptation with (f=114) and followed cognitive aptitude enhancement with f=95, then peer-learning (f=89), goal-setting (f=79). The least is relaxation and recreation with f=75. In connection with Curtis (2020), he emphasized that when students are solitary, they may contact educators at all hours, make many attempts to engage in nonacademic issues, and speak unfavorably about themselves.

In the case of **learning environment challenges**, the learners consider adaptation as the highest coping strategy with $f=71$, then goal- setting with $f=58$, followed by peer-learning (56), then relaxation and recreation ($f=56$) The least is in using cognitive aptitude enhancement with ($f=53$). This was relevant as what was stated in National Geographic (2016) that Wallace and Darwin both went beyond mere adaptation to describe how organisms adapt and evolve when they developed the notion of natural selection. Wallace believed that organism evolution was linked to organism adaptability to changing environmental conditions in some way.

When we consider which among coping strategies are the most useful, it is the **adaptation** that ranked first, followed by **cognitive aptitude enhancement**, then by **relaxation and recreation**. The fourth one is **goal- setting** and then the least is **peer-learning**.

Table 8. Difference in the Extent of Challenges Experienced by the Grade 9 learners in Tumbler District

Indicator	School					Remark
	I	II	III	F	p-	
	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	ratio	value	
Self-Regulation Challenges	3.12	3.13	2.70	1.068	.345	Not Significant
Technological Literacy and Competency	3.08	3.05	2.56	1.730	.179	Not Significant
Student Isolation	3.19	2.94	3.10	3.211	.042	Significant
Learning Resource	3.25	3.00	4.65	13.811	.000	Significant
Learning Environment	3.38	3.00	3.90	9.514	.000	Significant
Over-all	3.20	3.02	3.38	<u>4.063</u>	<u>.018</u>	Significant

Legend: I - Bawing National High School; II – Banisil National High School; III– Colot Aligado IP High School

It is shown in table 8 the extent of challenges experienced by the Grade 9 learners in Tumbler District. Over-all results reveal that **there is a significant difference** in the responses of Grade 9 learners as evidenced by an **F-ratio of 4.063 and a p-value of**

.018. A p-value of less .05 ($p=.018 < .05$) indicates that **the difference is significant.** The **learners in Colot Aligado IP School** have experienced the highest extent of challenges **with mean of 3.38** and the lowest extent of challenges with **mean of 3.02.** is experienced by the learners in **Banisil National High School.**

It is also noted that **student isolation** ($F = 3.211, p = .042$), **learning resource**, ($F = 13.811, p = .000$) , **learning environment** ($F = 9.514, p = .000$) remarked **significant.** It is still the learners in **Colot Aligado IP High School** who have experienced the **highest mean in learning resource and learning environment**, while the learners in **Bawing National High School** have experienced the highest in **student isolation.**

On the contrary, **the learners do not differ in their experienced** challenges in **self-regulation challenges** and **technological literacy and competency** as supported by a p-value of greater than .05.

Intervention Program

The study examined the remote learning challenges and most common coping mechanism of Grade 9 learners. Technological competency challenges was the least challenge met by the learners and the least strategy they used was peer-learning. To address the challenges, Synchronized Oral reading through Project E.D.O.N.G. was created. It is an acronym that stands for "Educational Dynamic Over-the-air Networked Guidance."

This innovative FM-based reading program is designed to provide educational support to individuals who lack reading fluency. Utilizing the power of radio waves, **E.D.O.N.G.** provides a unique platform for learning that is accessible to anyone with a radio receiver and/or lapel. The program is designed to promote literacy and enhance critical thinking skills, with a focus on providing learners with the tools they need to succeed. By harnessing the power of radio technology, it is helping to bridge the digital divide with the use of "Read After Me" Series of Dr. Genoveva Melendez Ablanque and provide a pathway to educational success for individuals around the world. The primary goal of Synchronized Oral Reading through Project E.D.O.N.G "Educational Dynamic Over-the-air Networked Guidance" session for learners of Banisil National High School can be a dynamic and engaging way to deliver content, particularly for learners who may struggle with traditional instructional methods. By using music, sound effects, and other multimedia elements, this project can help to capture students' attention and keep them engaged in the learning process. The impact of this will depend on a variety of factors, including the quality of the instructional materials, the expertise of the instructors, and the level of support provided to learners. However, by providing access to high-quality educational content and supporting learners' engagement and comprehension, Project EDONG can be an effective way to improve literacy outcomes and enhance educational opportunities for learners of all ages.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, it has been found that the learning environment of these learners is the biggest hindrance that they face. It is followed by self-regulation challenges or the personal struggles and difficulties they encounter in the remote learning setup. Meanwhile, learning resource challenges follow and technological competency challenges was the least challenge they met, respectively. The study discovered that adaption remains to most utilized strategy so that they can cope with isolation challenges, as inherently brought by the pandemic. It is followed by improving their cognitive skills so that they can learn even in the absence of teachers. The least strategy they used was peer-learning. Then, the study unveiled that there is a significant difference, the Grade 9 learners of Colot Aligado IP High School experience the severity of challenges that come along with the remote learning setup. However, this is no longer surprising. After all, the school is situated in a far-flung area, with limited to no access to the internet and other online infrastructures. On the flip side, the learners of Banisil National High School and Bawing National High School are slightly doing better in handling the challenges brought by remote learning. This is due to the proximity of the school to facilities and resources needed to execute online or modular learning.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings from the data, the researcher recommends that the teachers in the schools of Tambler District should employ Synchronized Oral Reading Through Project E.D.O.N.G and coordinate with the DepEd Division to tie up with corresponding departments and agencies, such as the Department of information and Communications Technology, to have a partnership with the Department of Education-Schools Division of General Santos City. This partnership entails a program that would enhance the technological literacy of the learners, especially those belong to remote areas. Since peer-learning is the least strategy used by learners. Learners must be encouraged to talk with one another, share ideas, and allow them to freely express their thoughts. Moreover, they should continually use the available tools to connect with their classmates, such as smartphones, laptops, and computers. Lastly, encourage the Department of Education to prioritize the development of these IP and far-flung schools, especially in the aspect of technology provision and literacy through synchronized oral reading through Project EDONG.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author had emphasized to the respondents that they don't have conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this endeavor. The author accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed

consent was given to each respondent before the conduct of the study. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality

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